

Environmental Management
Systems [EMS]
to regulate the widespread use of
synthetic textiles.

Renay Wells

renay.wells@griffithuni.edu.au

Master of Environment

Fashion Impact Specialist

www.fashionimpactspecialist.com

Sustainable Business | Climate Change Adaptation

1. Executive Summary:

Plastic waste generated from textile particulate matter (PM) has emerged as a critical global environmental concern (European Environment Agency, 2022; Forum for the Future, 2022). Research increasingly demonstrates that garments shed synthetic microfibrils (MFs) during domestic laundering, contributing to persistent microfiber pollution in terrestrial, aquatic, and atmospheric systems (De Falco et al., 2020; Singh et al., 2020; Surana et al., 2024). Fabrics such as polyester (PES), polyamide/nylon (PA), and elastane (EL), alongside their associated chemical leachates, are linked to bioaccumulation and biomagnification processes that threaten ecosystems and human health (Palacios-Mateo, 2021; Cao et al., 2024; Priya et al., 2023).

To address these risks, this paper argues that the textile and clothing (T&C) industry must urgently implement Cleaner Production (CP) practices supported by robust Environmental Management Systems (EMS). International standards—including ISO 14001:2015 (EMS), ISO 9001:2015 (Quality Management Systems), and ISO 14040:2006 (Life Cycle Assessment)—provide critical frameworks for reducing pollutive impacts and embedding sustainability across supply chains.

Environmental protection should be treated as an essential dimension of corporate social responsibility (CSR) for fashion brands and retailers. However, where voluntary action remains insufficient, regulatory intervention by governments and industry bodies such as the British Fashion Council (BFC) and the Australian Fashion Council (AFC) will be necessary to enforce systemic change (Benson, 2022; DCCEEW, 2023; The Guardian, 2024).

2. Acronyms:

AFC	Australian Fashion Council
BFC	British Fashion Council
CBA	Cost Benefit Analysis
CE	Circular Economy
CP	Cleaner Production
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
DCCEEW	Department of Climate Change, Energy, then Environment and Water
DPPs	Digital Product Passports
EEA	European Environment Agency
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EL	Elastane
EMS	Environmental Management Systems
EOL	End of Life
ESG	Environmental, Social and Governance
ESPR	Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation
FMPs	Fibrous Microplastics
GHGs	Greenhouse Gases
GSCM	Green Supply Chain Management
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
MF	Microfibre
PA	Polyamide/Nylon
PEF	Product Environmental Footprint
PEFCR	Product Environmental Footprint Category Rules
PES	Polyester
PM	Particulate Matter
QA	Quality Assurance
QC	Quality Control
QMS	Quality Management Systems
SA	Sustainability Assessment

SIP	Strategic Investment Program
SSC	Sustainable Supply Chains
SSCM	Sustainable Supply Chain Management
SM	Sustainable Manufacturing
T&A	Textile and Apparel
T&C	Textile and Clothing
TAF	Textile, Apparel, and Fashion
TQM	Total Quality Management
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
WHS	Workplace, Health, and Safety
WRAP	Waste and Resources Action Programme

Table of Contents:

1.	Executive Summary	page 2
2.	Acronyms	page 3
3.	Current Manufacturing Practices	page 6
3.1	Raw Materials : Synthetic Textiles	page 6
3.2	Finished Garments : Synthetic Clothing	page 6
4.	Urgency for Action	page 6
5.	Sustainable Supply Chain Management	page 7
5.1	Environmental Policy Planning	page 7
5.1.1	STRATEGY : ISO 14001	page 7
5.1.2	STRATEGY : ISO 9001	page 7
5.1.3	STRATEGY : ISO 14040	page 8
5.1.4	STRATEGY : ISO 14062	page 8
5.2	Implementation and Operation	page 9
5.2.1	ACHIEVE : ISO 14020	page 9
5.3	Internal Audits for Verification	page 9
5.3.1	EVALUATE : ISO 14030	page 9
6.	Management Review	page 10
7.	References	page 11

3. INTRODUCTION: Current Manufacturing Practices:

3.1 Raw Materials : Synthetic Textiles

Raw materials derived from crude oil and coal (Mondal et al., 2022) are used to produce polymers, processed into fibers, and subsequently knitted or woven into fabric. The production of these synthetic textiles advances environmental challenges due to their dependence on non-renewable resources (Muthu, 2020). Negative impacts associated with manufacturing processes include aspects of significant environmental harm; greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, toxic atmospheric pollutants (Hasanuzzaman & Bhar, 2016), and the release of fibrous microplastics (FMPs) into water sources during fabric dyeing and printing (Zhou et al., 2020). It is also important to acknowledge MF emissions are also associated with natural textiles compositions (Stanton et al, 2019; Stone et al., 2022).

3.2 Finished Garments : Synthetic Clothing

Fashion remains one of the most unsustainable industries both environmentally and socially (Geneva Environmental Network, 2024; Li et al., 2024; McFall-Johnsen, 2020). According to the 2023 Textile Exchange conference, global fiber production has nearly doubled from 58 million tonnes in 2000 to 116 million tonnes in 2022, with projections indicating it could reach 147 million tonnes by 2030 if current trends persist. With significant overconsumption of natural resources (European Parliament, 2020), water degradation, pollution, and energy-intensive production processes (Maiti, 2024). The rag trade requires an immediate overhaul, from design to development and its associated business models.

4. Urgency for Action:

It is morally and ethically imperative for fashion brands to implement environmental objectives and policies throughout their supply chains (Roberts-Islam, 2021). Undertaking internal audits to comprehend the consequences of their seasonal design choices and the impact of their production practices, including the effects of fabric and trim development, and end-of-life garment disposal (Payne, 2011). A focus solely on profit is insufficient to address the triple bottom line (Hiller Connell & Kozar, 2017). Embracing an understanding of

ecological and social dimensions, while adopting the principles of 'Conscious Capitalism' (Mackey & Sisodia, 2014) is crucial. A proactive approach by internal stakeholders will manage demand for product, profitability, compliance, and responsibility to balance environmental, social, and governance (ESG) standards.

5. Sustainable Supply Chain Management:

5.1 Environmental Policy Planning

5.1.1 STRATEGY : ISO 14001

To achieve green and continual improvement within the textile industry, it is essential to implement corrective measures and policies for sustainable supply chain management (SSCM) (Zimon, 2020). Setting comprehensive environmental planning objectives and practices (ISO, 2015) to address issues relating to textile waste (Khan et al., 2023), pollution emissions, and related aspects to the sustainable management (Zimon & Domingues, 2018) of MF emissions during production. Ethical leadership within governing organizations (Mansour et al., 2022) will incorporate social responsibilities. Driving corporate motivation and commitment to adopt advanced techniques (Hossain et al., 2024), and seizing opportunities for innovation (Todeschini et al., 2017). ISO 14001 is crucial to the mitigation of, and indirect risks associated with the prolonged use of synthetic fabrics.

BARRIERS to adoption : Previous studies into the economic performance (Li & Wu, 2017) of firms which have ratified EMS, found the substantial investment of EMS resulted in limited dividends (Iqbal et al, 2022). Therefore, we feel it is critical for governments of tiered textile nations to subsidise Strategic Investment Program (SIP) to align their nations to the UNEP Sustainability and Circularity in the Textile Value Chain – A Global Roadmap (2023). Aligning with two of the three priorities; improved practices and infrastructure investment.

5.1.2 STRATEGY : ISO 9001

Considered a catalyst for advancing social responsibility and environmentally friendly policies (Zimon et al., 2021), ISO 9001 can play a key role in the sustainable development of textiles and synthetic apparel items. Enhancing internal processes and support for

environmental objectives, a shift towards responsible and sustainable supply chains (SSC) (Gurzawska, 2019) will set parameters for the integrated management of quality control (QC) and quality assurance (QA). Improving sustainable production processes, fostering green innovation (Picaud-Bello et al., 2024), further enhancing the adoption of eco-practices. Total Quality Management (TQM) (Apparel Resources, 2015; Soltanmohammadi et al., 2021) will facilitate cooperation across all tiers of suppliers and external stakeholders (Zimon et al., 2020).

5.1.3 STRATEGY : ISO 14040

A certified life cycle assessment (LCA) approach for synthetic textiles and apparel (EEA, 2022), would find textile waste management following a circular practice of reuse and recycle (Abagnato et al., 2024). The Circular Economy (CE) is a pathway to sustainability within the industry (Chen et al., 2021), with a framework for ISO 14040:2006 covers LCA in addition to Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA). But can the textile industry use minimal resources in the production of garments and achieve little to no waste? Rahaman et al (2024) in their discussion of green production of textiles note that synthetics not only can be found in fiber form, but within the dyeing of fabrics.

Life Cycle Thinking in Textiles (UNEP, 2023) proposes enhancement of LCA within the industry, application of a Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) methodology allows for a metric-based approach to analysis, from raw material to recycling. Following the PEF Category Rules (PEFCR) would outline garment categorisation and comparison, cost optimisation, and eco-design. Ultimately ensuring brands follow a common structure to calculate environmental impacts and share product results. Platforms such as Carbonfact (Zamani, 2023) or long-term industry QA and QC auditing firm SGS, offer services to achieve environmental quality standards.

5.1.4 STRATEGY : ISO 14062

Fashion brands which substantially use virgin synthetic fabrications (DCCEEW, 2022), should urgently consider the principles of Design for Environment (DfE). Similarly to LCA, DfE analyses the environmental and workplace, health, and safety (WHS) issues across the lifespan of a product (Niinimäki, 2006). Although ISO 14062:2002 was withdrawn as a

standard, the concepts of eco-design remain relevant. Eco-responsible solutions (de Oliveira et al, 2021), discuss textile re-engineering as a sustainable option to be integrated into the design and development of apparel and synthetic textiles. Fibre to Fibre (F2F) innovation, finds Brisbane based firm BlockTexx®, able to assure textiles are fit for circularity (EEA, 2022). Safeguarding against the continued consumption of virgin fibres, enlarge the scope of the Eco-design for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) (European Commission, 2022), in the provision of secondary raw materials.

5.2 Implementation and Operation

5.2.1 ACHIEVE : ISO 14020

Communicating (ISO 14063:2020) the continual improvement of a brand's EMS and environmental compliance via eco-labelling (UNEP, 2024) and digital product passports (DPPs). Efficient processes within the production of garments, can verify circular production operations (Lindhahl, 2024), such as the use of recycled fabric contents, energy-efficient processes, or carbon footprints (Daphne, 2024). Industry 4.0 will be leveraged to not only improve operational performance (Fiorello et al., 2023) but in the gathering of data to legitimise environmental procurement, increasing transparency (Ospital et al., 2023). ISO 14020:2022 must be legislated and implemented industry wide, to end greenwashing and to regulate sustainability standards (Plakantonaki et al., 2023).

5.3 Internal Audits for Verification:

5.3.1 EVALUATE : ISO 14030

Environmental and social performance evaluation (ISO 14030-3:2022) should correspond with a firm's commitment to achieve environmental objectives and policies. Cost benefit analysis (CBA) (Camilleri, 2022 ; WRAP, 2023) and targets can quantify circular and sustainable manufacturing (SM) frameworks (Chourasiya et al., 2024). Identifying performance risks across all tiers of supply chains (Warasthe et al., 2022) to drive eco-sustainability (Patti et al., 2020), sustainability assessments (SA) (Gbolarumi et al, 2021) and Environmental Impact Assessments (EIA). Identifying and moderating Green Supply Chain

Management (GSCM) (Nazir et al., 2024) to address any gaps (Abbate et al., 2023) in the estimation of long-range MF pollution, and the extent to which carcinogenic exposure to synthetic textiles impacts the wearer. Long-term and indirect aspects should influence the future development of textile and apparel (T&A), from raw materials to end of life (EOL) waste management (Moazzem et al., 2021).

6. Management Review:

The Textile, Apparel, and Fashion (TAF) industry is marked by persistent claims of sustainability that often mask ongoing reliance on synthetic fabrics and associated pollution. Without the mandatory adoption of Environmental Management Systems (EMS) and the widespread integration of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) frameworks, the sector's pursuit of climate neutrality will remain unattainable. Continued dependence on synthetic fibres undermines ecological resilience and risks compromising the health and quality of life of future generations.

This paper argues that systemic change requires both regulatory intervention and industry-wide alignment with international standards to eliminate greenwashing and accelerate sustainable transformation. In the long term, a global phase-out of virgin synthetic materials should be considered an essential pathway toward safeguarding ecosystems and ensuring a genuinely sustainable fashion industry.

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